

Studies on 12-Heteropoly Niobomolybdate(VI)

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The nature and conditions of formation of 12-heteropoly niobomolybdate(VI) has been established by studying pH changes and thermometric titrations. Based on chemical and physical studies, the compound has been formulated as $K_{10}[MoNb_{12}O_{38}]34H_2O$. The important data on X-ray powder photography of the compound have been shown in the standard powder file. The thermal depolymerisation of the compound has been studied which indicated that the complete breakdown of the crystal lattice occurred at $750 \pm 5^\circ$.

A few heteropoly complexes of niobium was first reported by Lapitsku and his coworkers¹ with transition metal ions and also of Ce(III) as the heteroatom. These materials have very low niobium to central metal ratio ranging from 4 : 1 to 1 : 1. Dale et al² examined some of these complexes and in general have not found their works to be reproducible and reported 12-heteropoly niobomanganate (VI) successfully. In the present work, a new heteropoly compound $K_{10}[MoNb_{12}O_{38}]34H_2O$ is reported and characterised.

Experimental

If solutions of any arbitrary concentrations of the reactants are mixed together, they may cause immediate precipitation leading to the formation of a compound with indefinite composition. Hence working concentrations of the reactants have been chosen properly. Regarding the preparation of heteropoly acids or salts, a reference to older chemical literature would clearly show that the methods are based on trial and error or on conjecture. This investigation attempts to lay down some rigid conditions of preparation. To start with aqueous solutions of 0.1 M potassium hexaniobate ($K_6Nb_6O_{19} \cdot 16H_2O$), prepared freshly following the literature³ and 0.02 M molybdic acid ($H_2MoO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$, BDH grade) were found to be suitable for work. The studies on pH and thermometric titrations were carried with reactants in a similar way as discussed previously⁴. When 0.02 M molybdic acid solution was added gradually to 60 ml of 0.01 K-hexaniobate solution, a systematic decrease in pH from 10.8 to 8.2 was observed up to the addition of 12 ml of molybdic acid. It was followed then by a plateau of constant pH up to 20 ml of molybdic acid. Thermometric titrations^{4,5} corroborated the above result. The nature of the graphs were same as that of the previous communication⁴. From the studies of the graphs it might be inferred that some sort of compound formation might have been started in solution phase when 12 ml of molybdic acid was

added to 60 ml of K-hexaniobate solution and the formation ceased when 20 ml of molybdic acid was added to it. So the limiting volume (20 ml) of 0.02 M molybdic acid and 60 ml of 0.01 M K-hexaniobate solution was taken into consideration as the proper amount of reactants to be taken to extract the compound in solid phase. So a portion (20 ml) of 0.02 M molybdic acid was refluxed with 60 ml of 0.01 M K-hexaniobate solution for 4 hr, in a round bottom flask provided with a series of potash bulb guard tubes which absorbed CO_2 from air. Thus hydrolysis of alkali metal hexaniobate due to the presence of atmospheric CO_2 was easily avoided. The refluxed solution was then left in vacuum for 8 days when cream coloured powdery compound separated, which was washed several times with ether, dried and preserved for further study. The complete analysis of the compound was done by chemical and instrumental methods. Niobium was estimated gravimetrically⁶ by precipitating it as niobic acid with conc. HCl and then weighing as Nb_2O_5 at 850° . Molybdenum was estimated as molybdenyl oxinate⁷ by 8-hydroxyquinoline. Analytical values were checked up by colorimetric determinations⁸ of niobium and molybdenum by pyrogallol and potassium thiocyanate respectively at 450 m μ and 500 m μ . Potassium in the compound was estimated by perchloric method. Hydrogen was estimated by element estimation technique (Found : Nb, 39.44 ; Mo, 3.31 ; K, 12.93 ; H, 2.34%, Calcd. for $K_{10}[MoNb_{12}O_{38}]34H_2O$: Nb, 39.56 ; Mo, 3.40 ; K, 13.86 ; H, 2.41%). For assigning the molecular formula of the compound, the projection pattern of niobium and molybdenum with oxygen giving rise to the heteropoly complex anion $[MoNb_{12}O_{38}]^{10-}$ was taken into consideration. Following I.U.P.A.C. system the compound has been named as 12-heteropoly niobomolybdate(VI).

X-ray Powder Diffraction :

Failure to isolate a single crystal of the compound, we were compelled to take its X-ray powder

photographs. Some relevant data of the powder photograph of the compound have been entered in the form of a standard powder file as presented in X-ray powder file by ASTM*.

TABLE

K ₁₀ [MoNb ₁₂ O ₃₈]34H ₂ O 12-heteropoly niobomolybdate				
d	8.0	10.0	11.70	11.70
1/I ₀	100	28	27	27
Re	CuK=1.5405			
Filter - Ni	11.70	27	3.22	4
I/I ₀ visual strip measurement	10.0	28	3.13	8
Ref. Nil	10.0	15	3.12	26
	8.0	100	3.03	25
	8.5	25	3.00	7
System orthorhombic	7.7	25	2.95	8
a b c	7.0	25	2.12	4
	6.0	2	2.79	25
	5.9	10	2.75	8
	5.6	10	2.70	2
	5.4	15	2.62	2
D=3.62 gm ⁻¹ Sign+	5.3	2	2.45	25
Colour - Cream, Ref. Nil.	4.92	2	2.44	3
	4.9	3	2.33	3
Sample prepared in laboratory	4.75	10	2.35	2
analyses show	4.75	2	2.23	4
Nb=39, 46, H=2.34	4.16	7	2.27	2
Mo=3.31, K=12.93	3.75	25	2.23	3
Patter made at 25°C.				

* X-ray powder file of heteropoly niobomolybdate(VI)

The data on X-ray powder diffraction have been considered to be very much useful for the elucidation of structures and phases of heteropoly compounds. But the reports on standard powder files are very few⁹. The relevant data as obtained for niobomolybdate(VI) from a powder photograph have been entered in the form of a standard powder card in Table. On the first line of the card the interplaner spacing of the three most intense lines are arranged in order of the decreasing intensities; the fourth 'd' value is the largest observed spacing. The relative intensities (I/I₀) of these reflections are based on 100 for the strongest intensity observed are listed on the next line; directly below the corresponding 'd' values. The other lines of the card are self-explanatory.

Thermal Depolymerisation :

The prepared heteropoly compound can be regarded as a condensation heteroatomic inorganic polymer¹⁰. So its thermal depolymerisation studies have been carried on the light of the investigations made by West and Audrieth¹¹ on some heteropoly molybdic and tungstic acids. The compound was heated at different temperatures, followed by successive weighing using a thermogravimetric balance and estimating at every stage. The whole process involves the removal of water, followed at a much higher temperature by the complete breakdown of the crystal lattice. The decomposition of the compound started at 75° under reduced pressure when eight molecules of water were lost. At further

higher temperature, nearly at 150±5°, another nine molecules of water were lost. The rest of the seventeen water molecules remained intact in the crystal lattice till 370±5°. When the temperature was raised still higher, then nearly at 750±5°, complete break down of the crystal lattice of niobomolybdate(VI) was observed by finding the total loss in weight which was equivalent to seventeen molecules of water. From the residual mass, niobium, molybdenum and potassium were analysed as discussed above and from the determination of stoichiometric ratio between the metal and oxygen atom for their corresponding oxides, they were found to be present as Nb₂O₅, MoO₃ and K₂O respectively. Comparing the work of Babad-Zakhryapin¹² it may be argued that the water molecules in the compound can be considered to be zeolitic in character, occupying the relatively large interstices occurring in the structure of the heteropoly anion. Removal of water molecules does not alter the crystal lattice, but when breakdown of the latter occurs the edge-like structure rearranges to give a more compact crystalline product consisting largely of the oxides of niobium(V).

Discussion

Generally it is believed that for condensation process in heteropoly compounds, it is necessary to maintain acid medium⁴. However, in the present study the formation of K₁₀[MoNb₁₂O₃₈]34H₂O, took place in the basic medium (pH 8.2). The formation in presence of OH⁻ ions may be compared with the catalytic behaviour of the OH⁻ ions in the base catalysed aldol condensation. It may be predicted that in the formation of this type of heteropoly compound, OH⁻ ions behave as catalyst and the resultant compound might be the polyhedra of the oxides of niobium and molybdenum resulting from the elimination of H₂O molecules. From the slight hint that may be had from the work of Lindqvist¹³ it may be predicted that two units of isopoly [Nb₆O₁₃]⁶⁻ arrange themselves in such a way through oxygen linkage so that there is a vacant room of octahedral size to accommodate Mo⁶⁺ forming 12-heteropoly niobomolybdate(VI).

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